

ISic0175

I.Sicily inscription 0175

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

tuff

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Found in Termini Imerese in 1783

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 44 cm

Width 31 cm

Depth 14 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]a[---]
2. A(ulus) Fabricius A(uli) f(ilius)
3. Primus
4. Postumia
5. Fausta
6. Fabricia

Apparatus

Text from ILTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285260

EDR 127475

EDCS 22100106

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7404 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bivona, L. 1994. *Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica.* Palermo / Rome. At 97

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